

MATERIAL CHARACTERIZATION OF THIN FILM PIEZOELECTRIC POLYMERS

Frank Holloway¹ and Aleksandra M. Vinogradov¹

¹ *Department of Mechanical and Industrial Engineering, Montana State University, Bozeman, MT 59717 USA*

SUMMARY: The paper describes an experimental program developed to characterize the material properties of thin film piezoelectric polymers PVF₂, a co-polymer of PVDF (polyvinylidene fluoride). These unidirectional materials have been used as active elements in composite devices for noise suppression and position control. Static and dynamic test results presented in the paper indicate that the mechanical response of PVF₂ thin films at room temperature is time-dependent. The creep rates tend to accelerate at elevated temperatures. It is shown that within certain limits, i.e., approximately 57% of yield stress, the properties of the material can be described by the constitutive equations of linear hereditary viscoelasticity. Above this limit, a stress-dependent nonlinear viscoelastic theory must be used to characterize the properties of piezoelectric thin films.

KEYWORDS: piezoelectric polymers, thin films, creep, viscoelasticity

INTRODUCTION

Piezoelectric materials have been extensively used in the design of intelligent structures. Such structures represent hybrid composite systems used in a variety of applications including vibration control, noise suppression, alignment precision control and damage detection. In general, active control devices are designed in the form of laminated composites the response of which directly depends on the material properties of their piezoelectric components.

In general, piezoelectric materials include piezoelectric ceramics and polymers that produce measurable electrical charges in response to mechanical stress. Because of the brittle nature of ceramics, piezoelectric polymers such as polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) and its co-polymer PVF₂ are often used to design compliant sensors and actuators. Typically, piezoelectric polymers are formed in thin films which are electrically poled in one or two directions. In practice, such materials are treated as linearly elastic, and their constitutive properties are defined by the Hooke's law coupled with piezoelectric relations [1].

However, experimental evidence suggests that the mechanical properties of PVF₂ thin films are time-dependent. Samples of this material tested at room temperature under sustained loading conditions develop creep deformations. Hence, it is critical in terms of accurate analysis and design of adaptive structures to fully understand and adequately describe the mechanical response of piezoelectric polymers. The objective of this study is to characterize the creep properties of PVF₂ thin films through a consistent experimental program leading to the development of an accurate constitutive model of this material.

THEORETICAL APPROACH

In many applications, the creep properties of polymers at room temperature can be defined by the constitutive equations of linear hereditary viscoelasticity [2,3]. The theory is based on the Boltzmann's superposition principle leading to the stress-strain relation in the form

$$\sigma = R^* [\epsilon] \quad (1)$$

where R^* denotes a linear integral operator of the Stieltjes convolution type

$$R^* = E \left(1 - \frac{1}{E} \int_0^t R(t-\tau) d\tau \right) \quad (2)$$

In Eqn 2, the kernel $R(t)$ represents the relaxation properties of the material.

An alternative viscoelastic constitutive equation can be presented in the form

$$\epsilon(t) = \sigma D(t) + \int_0^t D(t-\tau) \frac{d\sigma}{d\tau} d\tau \quad (3)$$

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where the time-dependent material response to a given stress history $\sigma(t)$ is defined by the function $D(t)$ known as the creep compliance. This function is determined experimentally, typically, from static tension/compression creep tests conducted under sustained loading conditions with $\sigma = \sigma_s = \text{const}$, in which case Eqn 3 reduces to

$$\epsilon(t)/\sigma_s = D(t) \quad (4)$$

It is clear that $D(t)$ must be independent of the experimental stress level σ_s , alternatively, if the creep compliance is shown to depend on stress, the assumptions of linear viscoelastic theory become invalid, and a nonlinear theory must be used to characterize the time-dependent properties of the material [4-6].

An alternative dynamic testing procedure for material characterization of polymers can be used to directly determine the creep or relaxation properties of the material. In this case, samples are subjected to harmonic oscillations, and the material response is defined in terms of a complex modulus or a complex creep compliance. In particular, the complex modulus in the frequency domain is of the form

$$\tilde{E}(\omega) = E'(\omega) + iE''(\omega) \quad (5)$$

where the storage and loss moduli E' and E'' are defined by

$$E'(\omega) = \frac{\sigma^o}{\epsilon^o} \cos \delta ; \quad E''(\omega) = \frac{\sigma^o}{\epsilon^o} \sin \delta \quad (6)$$

In Eqn 6, σ^0 and ε^0 denote, respectively, stress and strain amplitudes, and δ is the phase angle between stress and strain. Note that, in general, σ^0 and δ are functions of ω .

Substitution of experimentally determined σ^0 and δ for each prescribed value of ε^0 into Eqn 6 provides the functions $E'(\omega)$ and $E''(\omega)$ over the experimental range of frequencies. On this basis, the relaxation function in Eqn 2 can be obtained by the inverse Fourier transformation from the frequency domain to the time domain.

The above method, however, requires that a large volume of experimental data be obtained over a wide range of frequencies because the time range of the transformed functions is that of $1/\omega$. This, in turn, requires an extensive long-term testing program.

Typically, the effectiveness of the dynamic testing technique can be enhanced by utilizing the properties of thermorheologically simple viscoelastic materials, [2,7]. This class of materials is characterized by an experimentally determined function, known as the shift factor a_T , that allows to determine the properties of the material at any temperature T from the respective properties measured at a reference temperature T_0 by expanding or compressing the time scale proportionally to a_T . Based on this property, known as the time-temperature correspondence principle, the frequency range of the complex modulus in Eqn 5 can be expanded using the relation

$$\tilde{E}(\omega, T) = \tilde{E}(\omega a_T, T_0) \quad (7)$$

Once the complex modulus $\tilde{E}(\omega)$ is obtained over an expanded frequency range, the complex compliance of the material can be obtained in the form

$$\check{D}(\omega) = D'(\omega) + iD''(\omega) \quad (8)$$

where $D'(\omega)$ and $D''(\omega)$ denote the storage and loss compliances related to E' and E'' by

$$D'(\omega) = \frac{1}{E'(\omega)[1 + \tan^2 \delta]} \quad (9)$$

$$D''(\omega) = \frac{1}{E''(\omega)[1 + \tan^2 \delta]} \quad (10)$$

Similarly to transforming the relaxation function from the frequency domain to the time domain, the creep compliance of the material as a function of time can be obtained from Eqn 8 using inverse Fourier transformation.

Determination of both the relaxation modulus and creep compliance completes the material characterization based on linear viscoelastic theory.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

As a first step in this study, a series of static tests were conducted in order to determine the range of stresses for which the creep compliance is stress independent. Within this range, linear viscoelastic theory can be used to characterize the material properties of PVF₂. With

this objective, creep tests of (2.54x10.16) cm PVF₂ thin film samples at constant stress levels ranging from 13.8 % to 122.1 % of the yield stress were performed for 2 hour durations. The results of these tests have identified the response range for linear viscoelastic characterization.

Further, a dynamic testing program was developed to determine the complex modulus of PVF₂ thin film in the frequency domain. Material samples with dimensions (10.16x2.54) cm and thickness of 20 μ were subjected to a prescribed loading history involving certain prestress conditions to insure tensile deformations with superimposed oscillatory strain of relatively small amplitude. The testing apparatus shown in Fig. 1 was designed to allow control of the prestress level using an adjustable grip, and to apply harmonic strain using a digitally controlled electrodynamic vibration exciter. A temperature chamber was used for temperature control.

Dynamic tests were conducted at a constant temperature, a constant prestress level of 20 % of yield stress, a constant strain amplitude of 0.073%, and frequencies ranging from 6.3 rad/sec to 315 rad/sec. An in-line load cell, and a temperature and phase compensated LVDT were used to

Fig. 1: Testing apparatus.

record the response of PVF₂ samples in terms of the phase angle δ and the stress-strain amplitude ratio σ^0/ϵ^0 as defined by Eqn 6.

Finally, in order to expand the experimental range of frequencies using the time-temperature correspondence principle, each set of experiments was repeated at elevated temperatures in the range from 25.5°C to 81.1°C

Fig 2: Creep compliance of PVF₂

Fig. 3: Dynamic storage and loss moduli for PVF₂ (25.5°C and 23.5% yield)

RESULTS

Resulting from static creep tests, the creep compliance $D(t)$ of PVF₂ has been determined for different stresses σ_s , as shown in Fig. 2. From these diagrams it is clear that, for stresses below 57% of the yield stress, the creep compliance $D(t)$ is stress independent. Respectively, within this range, the theory of linear viscoelasticity can be used to characterize PVF₂ thin film.

Further, dynamic tests of PVF₂ samples at room temperature and different frequencies has allowed to determine the storage and loss moduli E' and E'' , as defined by Eqn 6. These results, plotted on a log-log scale are presented in Fig. 3.

Fig. 4. Dynamic storage modulus for PVF₂ at elevated temperatures.

Fig. 5: Temperature dependent shift factor

Repetition of the same set of dynamic experiments under elevated temperature conditions has provided the following results: the storage and loss elastic moduli as functions of frequency and temperature, see Fig. 4, and the shift factor $a_T(T)$ over the temperature range shown in Fig. 5.

Based on this information, dynamic storage and loss compliances have been determined in the frequency domain using Eqns 9 and 10. These results are presented in Figs. 6 and 7.

Fig. 6: Shifted dynamic storage compliance : 25.5°C - 81.1°C

Fig. 7: Shifted Dynamic Loss Compliance : 25.5°C - 81.1°C

Finally, analytical functions obtained by a curve fit of data shown in Figs. 6 and 7 have been used to obtain the creep compliance $D(t)$ in the time domain through an approximate transformation by Ninomiya and Ferry [2] in the form

$$D(t) = D'(\omega) + 0.40D''(0.40\omega) - 0.014D''(10\omega) \Big|_{\omega=1/t} \quad (11)$$

This creep compliance, obtained on the basis of dynamic tests, has been used to predict the creep behavior of thin film PVF₂ for the time duration of 1.92×10^6 sec (about 22 days). An analytical function in the form

$$D(t) = 3.424 (t^{0.0006} - 0.991) \times 10^{-8} \tag{12}$$

has been found to provide the best curve fit for the creep compliance of the material.

Fig. 8: Comparison of static and dynamic test results

A comparison of the creep curves obtained from the dynamic and static tests shown in Fig. 8 indicates that, within the range of stresses up to 57% of the yield stress, both experimental methods provide practically identical results. Above this limit, the dynamic testing technique predicts lower creep rates than those obtained from the static experiments. These latter results confirms that below the indicated stress limit the creep properties of PVF₂ can be characterized using the constitutive equations of linear viscoelasticity.

CONCLUSIONS

The results of this study clearly indicate that the mechanical response of piezoelectric polymers PVF₂ is time dependent. Linear viscoelastic theory based on the Boltzmann's superposition principle can be used to characterize the creep properties of the material for stresses below 57% of the yield stress. In the temperature range from 25 °C to 81 °C piezoelectric thin films PVF₂ can be treated as thermorheologically simple materials that follow the time-temperature correspondence principle. It is shown that within the indicated range of stresses, both static and dynamic test results are in good agreement. Based on these results, a power function has been used to describe the creep compliance of PVF₂.

It is important to note that the development of a complete constitutive model of piezoelectric polymers requires further research. In particular, an expanded experimental program is required to obtain the nonlinear viscoelastic stress-strain-time relations that will accurately describe the time dependent response of the material beyond the applicability range of the linear viscoelastic theory. In addition, research must be also directed towards time-dependent material characterization of piezoelectric coefficients that determine coupling effects between

electrical and mechanical responses of the material. However, such objectives remain out of the scope of present work.

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